

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

IMPACT OF SARS-COV-2 ON THE HUMAN DIGESTIVE SYSTEM

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Abstract

COVID-19 is a pandemic caused by severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2). Early reported symptoms include fever, cough, and respiratory symptoms. There were few reports of digestive symptoms. However, with COVID-19 spreading worldwide, symptoms such as vomiting, diarrhoea, and abdominal pain have gained increasing attention. Research has found that angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 (ACE2), the SARS-CoV-2 receptor, is strongly expressed in the gastrointestinal tract and liver. Whether theoretically or clinically, many studies have suggested a close connection between COVID-19 and the digestive system. In this review, we summarize the digestive symptoms reported in existing research, discuss the impact of SARS-CoV-2 on the gastrointestinal tract and liver, and determine the possible mechanisms and aetiology, such as cytokine storm. In-depth exploration of the relationship between COVID-19 and the digestive system is urgently needed.

Keywords: COVID-19; gastrointestinal tract; gut-lung axis; inflammatory cytokine storm; liver injury.

COVID-19, which is caused by SARS-CoV-2, is a significant global public health problem. SARS-CoV-2 belongs to the beta coronavirus family, which enters cells through the ACE2 receptor [1]. Symptoms involving the digestive system were not evident among patients suffering from the initial disease in Wuhan, China. Only 2.6% had diarrhoea and 2.0% had chronic diseases of the liver [2]. As the case complexity grows, more and more patients have reported digestive system symptoms. The disorder, with diarrhoea arising most often, is marked by diarrhoea, anorexia, nausea, vomiting, abdominal discomfort, and gastrointestinal bleeding. Several potential mechanisms for the development of gastrointestinal problems have been suggested. These include virus-induced cytopathic impacts through ACE2, immune-mediated inflammatory cytokine storm, the function of the gut-lung axis as well as drug-related harm. These pathways can also contribute to sepsis and acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS), which are the leading causes of death in COVID-19 patients. However, the original underlying conditions can impact patient treatment and prognosis not only in COVID-19 cases but also in gastrointestinal diseases.

The liver is the body's largest digestive gland for biligenesis and detoxification. Liver damage is sometimes identified as a typical occurrence in COVID-19 patients. Through pathology and blood tests, the mechanisms of liver injury mainly arise from direct viral infection, drug cytotoxicity, and inflammatory immune response. Alternative explanations include hypoxic hepatitis, hepatic congestion related to mechanical ventilation (PEEP), and gut barrier dysfunction [3]. Indeed, notable facts include the identification of ACE2-positive cells in liver tissues, which turn the liver into a potential target for SARS-CoV-2 infection. Moreover, it has been shown that the associations between prior liver diseases and COVID-19 will contribute to worse clinical outcomes and should be taken seriously during

care. Specifically, we focus on liver transplant recipients with COVID-19 due to their altered immune state and disease susceptibility. Further studies in COVID-19 patients call for a better understanding of pathogenesis and for optimal treatment of COVID-19.

Based on the above statement, we propose that the development and progression of COVID-19 are closely related to the gastrointestinal tract and the liver. However, there are currently few studies available; thus, this article summarizes the relevant views and suggests potential mechanisms.

COVID-19 typically develops in patients as a respiratory disease, with some patients reporting gastrointestinal symptoms during disease episodes such as diarrhoea, anorexia, nausea, vomiting, stomach discomfort, and gastrointestinal bleeding. Diarrhoea, with a rate ranging from 2.0 to 47.9%, is the most commonly reported gastrointestinal symptom in COVID-19 patients [4-10]. Even though the first COVID-19 clinical article reported that only 1 in 38 patients had diarrhoea [5], the frequency of diarrhoea is usually greater in later stages. A cohort of 73 COVID-19 patients showed that diarrhoea was observed in up to 35.6% of patients [9]. Similarly, the incidence of diarrhoea was up to 47.9% in a cohort of 305 patients [7].

Although rarely reported, anorexia can occur frequently once diagnosed. Wang et al. reported an incidence of up to 39.9% and Fang et al. reported 33.1% [7, 8]. According to data, patients with nausea account for 1.0-9.3% [6-10]. Vomiting, stomach discomfort and gastrointestinal bleeding can also be observed in COVID-19 patients, though with a low incidence. Regarding the available clinical studies, gastrointestinal symptoms are relatively common in patients with COVID-19, even though they only manifest in some cases [11].

In terms of pathology experiments, Xiao et al. [9] showed that H&E staining of the oesophagus, stomach, duodenum, and rectum showed no substantial mucosal

epithelial harm. Occasional lymphocyte infiltration was observed in the oesophageal squamous epithelium in this study. Although the lamina propria of the uterus, duodenum, and rectum were found to display an excess of infiltrating plasma cells and interstitial oedema lymphocytes, ACE2 was rarely expressed in the oesophagus epithelium but abundant in the glandular epithelia cilia and in gastric and intestinal epithelial cell cytoplasm. The virus nucleocapsid protein, although not in the oesophageal epithelial cell, was found in the gastric, duodenal and rectal glandular cytoplasm. This means that SARS-CoV-2 could directly target gastrointestinal cells, especially gastric and intestinal epithelial cells, leading to inflammatory reactions.

Research has shown that SARS-CoV-2 enters cells through the ACE2 receiver [3]. Immunofluorescence data have shown that ACE2 protein is abundantly expressed in gastric, duodenal, and rectal epithelial glandular cells, which promotes the possible entry of SARS-CoV-2 into host cells [9]. Moreover, a study has suggested a possible mechanism for the digestive symptoms in COVID-19 patients. ACE2 expression on the small intestine surface cells can mediate viral invasion and expansion, triggering gastrointestinal inflammation [12]. SARS-CoV-2 invades intestinal cells expressing ACE2, causing malabsorption, intestinal disorders, activation of the enteric nervous system, and, ultimately, diarrhoea. Interestingly, a previous study on other coronaviruses found that human intestinal epithelial cells' high sensitivity to coronavirus increases their replicative capacity [13].

Approximately 34.5% of 197 patients showed neutrophilia [14], which is known to be a trigger for ARDS and sepsis growth in COVID-19 patients. Secondary hemophagocytic lymph histiocytosis (SHLH), an underrecognized hyperinflammatory syndrome, could also be a major factor in the development of COVID-19 as SHLH, which can cause fatal and fulminant multiorgan failure hypercytokinemia [15].

In one clinical study, a high degree of IL-1B, IFN- τ , IP-10, and monocyte chemotactic protein 1 (MCP-1) expression has been reported in infected patients [4]. These inflammatory cytokines can cause unique immune activation and activate Type 1 helper cells (Th1). Several reports have also shown that cytokine rates in COVID-19 patients are positively associated with disease severity [16].

Cytokine storm is correlated with the development of ARDS and multiple organ insufficiency outside the lung during COVID-19 progression [17]. Cytokine storms can also be a cause of worsening in COVID-19 patients, including those with gastrointestinal diseases.

China's Diagnosis and Treatment Protocol for COVID-19 indicates that maintaining the intestinal microecological balance is one way to prevent secondary bacterial infections in COVID-19 patients. The role of the gastrointestinal tract and intestinal microbiota is closely linked. Although independent of one another, the digestive and respiratory tracts will influence each other through the gut-lung axis [18].

Although a limited case series from China reported that certain COVID-19 patients had decreased *Lactobacillus* and *Bifidobacterium* microbial dysbiosis

[19], no definite research has shown that the intestinal microbiota is indeed linked to COVID-19. Nevertheless, previous research has shown that ACE2, the SARS-CoV-2 receptor, can adjust intestinal microbe homeostasis through amino acids [20]. Strong microbiota may ferment to generate fatty acids (SCFAs), and most SCFAs are metabolized. Unmetabolized SCFAs promote the development of naive CD4 + T cells to regulate cells in the peripheral circulation and bone marrow. Thus, immune response in the lungs would be impaired if the intestinal microbiota stability is disrupted.

Cytokines and inflammatory cells increase in COVID-19 patients, which is correlated with sepsis and ARDS complications [17, 18]. Studies have shown that cytokine storms can be inhibited by butyric acid provided by the intestinal microbiota [21]. Therefore, the incidence of sepsis and ARDS may be minimized by the intestinal microbiota, both of which have a high mortality risk in COVID-19. Moreover, some researchers consider the connection between sepsis and intestinal microbiota disorders to be jointly promoted [22]. This indicates that disease of the gastrointestinal microbiota causes the development of sepsis, and in effect, the stable structure of the intestinal microbiota is disrupted, followed by the creation of a destructive cycle.

Previous reports have shown that approximately 60% of patients with SARS developed liver damage, and RT-PCR detected positive SARS-CoV in liver tissues [23, 24]. Similar to SARS-CoV, evidence has emerged that SARS-CoV-2 is associated with hepatic injury. According to the relevant data, the proportion of COVID-19 patients with various degrees of hepatic injury was estimated at 58%-78% [25]. Studies have found that some patients with COVID-19 had increased aspartate aminotransferase (AST) and alanine aminotransferase (ALT) levels, both of which displayed mild elevation [4, 6]. Furthermore, Zhang et al. [26] found that gamma-glutamyl transferase (GGT) was increased in 30 (54%) of 56 COVID-19 patients. They also suggested that COVID-19 patients may have a higher overall bilirubin levels and lower serum albumin. Similarly, Zhou et al. found that elevated ALT levels and a reduced platelet count and albumin were correlated with a higher death rate [27]. For COVID-19 cases, liver damage is typically moderate and does not generally require care [28]. However, a case of severe liver damage with serum AST and ALT levels up to 1445 U/L and 7590 U/L, respectively, was also reported [6]. Parohan et al. [29] analysed 3,428 COVID-19 patients including 1,455 severe cases. Significantly higher serum AST, ALT, and total bilirubin levels but lower serum albumin levels were found in the severe group. Moreover, activation of coagulation and fibrinolysis accompanied by thrombocytopenia was observed in severe COVID-19 cases [8]. Liver damage can be aggravated by the increase of COVID-19 infection severity, which indicates that the degree of liver damage may serve as an indicator of COVID-19 progression.

Autopsies of COVID-19 patients have provided conclusive evidence of secondary hepatic injury. Xu et al. [30] conducted an autopsy on a 50-year-old woman who died of COVID-19. The results revealed that the

patient had severe microvascular steatosis and mild liver lobular and portal activity. Liu et al. [31] autopsied a COVID-19 patient who was referred to the hospital for multiple cerebral infarction. They observed a grey liver and a swollen gallbladder, but there was no sign of liver failure. Wichmann et al. [32] conducted autopsies on many COVID-19 events with pre-existing cardiac disease and found hepatomegaly, persistent inflammation, and fatty change. The current sample size has been small, and more histological samples are needed to understand the pathological changes in the liver due to SARS-CoV-2.

As mentioned above, SARS-CoV-2 uses the same receptor, ACE2, as SARS-CoV, which leads to direct infection of ACE2-positive cells [3]. Existing studies have shown that ACE2 is abundantly expressed on liver cells (2.6%), bile duct cells (59.7%) and liver endothelial cells [33, 34]. Chai et al. found that ACE2 expression levels in bile duct cells were slightly higher than those in liver cells and were comparable with alveolar epithelial type II cells. Given that bile duct cells play an important role in immune defence and liver regeneration, their impairment may serve as a major cause of virus-induced hepatic injury in COVID-19 patients [33].

Available COVID-19 data indicate that hepatic injury may be mediated through direct virus-induced cytopathogenic effects. Wang et al. identified typical coronavirus particles characterized by spiked structures in the cytoplasm of hepatocytes. The ultrastructure of SARS-CoV-2-infected liver cells included endoplasmic reticulum expansion, mitochondrial swelling and a decrease in glycogen granules. Moreover, wide apoptosis of liver cells and abnormal binuclear cells were observed, with a paucity of CD4+ and CD8+ lymphocytes identified via immunohistochemistry [35]. In summary, these findings suggested typical hepatic injury characterized by viral infection. A previous study on SARS-associated viral hepatitis found significantly increased mitotic cells, eosinophilic bodies, and balloon-like liver cells in the liver [24], which also indicated liver cell apoptosis and thereby the triggering of hepatic injury. Further research on the pathology of impaired livers in COVID-19 patients is urgently required.

In short, it is not sensible to disregard the potential function of SARS-CoV-2 in the gastrointestinal tract and liver. It may enter cells directly via the ACE2 receptor, and thereby influences the usual operation of the gastrointestinal tract and liver. Different mechanisms, such as cytokine storm, the gut-lung axis, etc., are also possible. In the meantime, disorders of the digestive system and COVID-19 are frequently linked, can worsen patient prognosis, and increase the likelihood of death. The underlying mechanisms of the interaction between COVID-19 and digestive system diseases are still not precise. Thus, we hope that future studies focus on this issue and propose more effective preventive measures, medical treatments, and clinical strategies.

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